

REAL-TIME PROCESS MONITORING OF 3D PRINTED MULTILAYERED STRUCTURES USING OPTICAL FIBER BRAGG GRATING SENSORS

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ABSTRACT

The additively manufactured parts and components present many important advantages arising from the potentiality of building functional parts with intricate design features and locally defined mechanical properties. Despite the enormous progress that these technologies have presented over recent years there are still aspects of great interest that must be studied. In Fused Deposition Modeling (FDM), as in other LM processes, the heating and rapid cooling cycles of the work materials provoke non-uniform thermal gradients and cause stress build-up that consequently result in part distortions and dimensional inaccuracy. Once the building process is completed, the FDM built part can be viewed as a laminate composite structure with anisotropic material properties. As a result, real-time monitoring is essential for the evaluation and control of the final parts' quality that could lead to significant improvements. The present work investigates the incorporation of optical fiber Bragg grating (FBG) sensors for real-time monitoring of strain build up during the fabrication procedure. The developed residual strains were recorded using short single mode optical sensors as well as a series of five multiplexed Bragg gratings, each one operating at a different wavelength, inscribed on the same optical fiber. These sensors were embedded at various locations within the middle plane of thin plate specimens built using FDM process. Temperature mapping of the fabricated specimens during the deposition process was also performed. It is demonstrated from the experimental results that the magnitude of the induced residual strains is significant during material consolidation of deposited layers.

1 INTRODUCTION

Additive/Layered/Rapid Manufacturing (AM/LM/RM) technologies or solid freeform fabrication (SFF) process are widely being used because of their ability to create objects of high complexity in geometry, which are impossible to be manufactured via the subtractive methods. Additionally, through the use of the AM/LM/RM technologies is feasible to fabricate functional parts with tailored mechanical properties and customized components can be manufactured as end use parts. In recent years, these technologies have been employed in many industries such as aircraft, automotive, aerospace, architecture, medical and dental industry. As a result, parts are produced automatically and rapidly without any tooling requirement and human interface. The representative examples of Layered Manufacturing processes are Fused Deposition Modeling (FDM), Stereolithography Apparatus (SLA), Selective Laser Sintering (SLS) and Laminated Object Manufacturing (LOM).

The FDM is one of the most promising methods included in this category, because of its speed and cost-effectiveness. Physical objects can be produced via the FDM technology directly from computer-aided design (CAD) files. The designed geometric model is imported into a software program (i.e. Catalyst Ex), which mathematically slices the model into horizontal layers and predefined deposition paths are created [1]. In the FDM technique the model material which is widely used is thermoplastic, such as the commercial Acrylonitrile Butadiene Styrene (ABS) and the Polylactic Acid (PLA). The FDM manufactured parts are produced by the sequential deposition of material layers one upon the other. During the building process the model material which is in the form of a flexible filament is fed

into a machine via a specific roller mechanism and then is extruded through a heated nozzle onto the building platform. The molten material that is deposited, quickly cools, solidifies and bonds with the adjacent rasters. After the completion of a whole layer build, the worktable is moved downwards one road height in order to accept the extruded material of the next layer [2-3]. The bonding mechanism between the individual roads of the same layer and of the neighboring layers is driven by the thermal energy of semi-molten material. Once the building procedure is completed, the FDM fabricated part can be considered as a laminate composite structure of partially bonded rasters with anisotropic material properties.

Despite the evolution and the advantages that additive manufacturing technologies have offered to the engineering, medical applications as well as in many other fields, there are still aspects of great interest that should be investigated. Additively manufactured components exhibit many quality issues, such as delamination of layers, material volumetric shrinkage, thermal stresses and strains, undesired porosity, deformation, voids, poor surface finish and geometrical inaccuracy. All these defects mainly resulting from the chosen processing parameters which in many cases are not specified and for that reason, they should be selected following several trial and error experiments. Layered manufacturing processes and consequently FDM technique are characterized by the development of residual stresses and strains due to the manufacturing procedure which is followed. For that reason, many researchers have focused their studies on predicting and evaluating the induced residual stresses and strains arising from the building process [4-7]. The probable non-uniform stresses and strains which are developed during the fabrication procedure due to the contraction of the deposited material that solidifies, can affect the geometrical accuracy of the manufactured component, the final part's quality and cause phenomena of inner and intra layer delamination, warpage as well as cracking. Additionally, temperature gradients are taking place due to the subsequent deposition of heated material which is cooled and then reheated. These temperature variations can also lead to the development of residual stresses and strains that are aggregated with those from local changes in the mechanical properties of material. Based on the above, an important conclusion exported is that real-time monitoring and control of developed strains and temperature changes during the building process is essential. This can help to the collection of significant information concerning building parameters mainly affecting the final mechanical response of the fabricated structure, such as the bonding quality of the adjacent rasters and the component's temperature history.

In our days not many non-invasive methods are available for real-time monitoring and quality control during the fabrication process of elements constructed via the FDM technique or in general, the layered manufacturing technologies. Thus, the embedment of fiber optic sensors within structures, in order to be used as sensing tools for real-time measurements of strain fields build up and temperature variations monitoring, appears to be a highly innovative method. Furthermore, many works have been reported that include the use of fiber Bragg grating (FBG) sensors for in-situ curing monitoring in polymeric and composite materials [8-10]. In [11] the magnitude of the in-situ solidification induced residual strains is investigated in FDM built parts manufactured using different processing parameters. A fiber Bragg grating was embedded in the mid-plane of FDM built prismatic specimens, in order to record the developed residual strains at the end of the fabrication process. The same specimens were subsequently subjected to a thermal cycle, below the material's glass-transition temperature, where their coefficient of thermal expansion (CTE) was measured using the FBG sensor. In [12] a partially embedded long fiber Bragg grating into an epoxy cylindrical specimen was used to monitor the strain distribution evolution along its axis when subjected cycles of thermal ageing at 70°C and 110°C. Using strain data from the FBG, the coefficient of thermal expansion was evaluated. Based on the strain data from the FBG, numerical simulations of an equivalent thermo-elastic matrix were performed to obtain the residual stresses in the specimen at the end of the thermal cycles. The results demonstrated the capability of FBG sensors in providing important information on the degree of cure and evolution of fabrication induced strains inside the epoxy. Moreover, in [13] a method based on the dual-configuration FBG sensor is proposed to measure the coefficients of the thermal expansion and hygroscopic swelling (CHS) of polymeric materials. In [14] the photo-polymerization induced shrinkage strains in two photopolymers commonly used in the laser based stereolithography process were investigated. A FBG sensor was utilized for the effective determination of the resulted shrinkage

strains throughout the consolidation process of cast built test specimens, upon exposure to UV light of specific irradiation intensity.

Taking into account some very important advantages of the FBG sensors, such as their fast response, high sensitivity, signal integrity, long-term stability, multifunctionality, long transmission distance, multiplexing capabilities and good corrosion resistance, it is easily understood why these sensing systems have turned into highly attractive process monitoring tools in many applications, such as in aircraft and helicopter structures, composite strain monitoring, bridge monitoring, pipeline security monitoring as well as structural health monitoring [15]. As a result, the use of such sensing tools can greatly contribute towards the notion of intelligent structures, allowing real-time monitoring of important parameters at critical parts which are inaccessible to conventional sensors.

The main objective of the present study is the incorporation of optical fiber Bragg grating sensors, in order to investigate in real-time the strain field build up during the FDM fabrication procedure. The developed residual strains were recorded using short single mode optical sensors, as well as a series of five multiplexed Bragg gratings, each one operating at a different wavelength, inscribed on the same optical fiber. These sensors were embedded at various locations within the middle plane of thin plate specimens built via the FDM process. Furthermore, temperature mapping of the fabricated specimens during the deposition procedure was also performed. It is demonstrated from the experimental results that the magnitude of the induced residual strains is significant during material consolidation of deposited layers.

2 FIBER BRAGG GRATING SENSORS

Fiber Bragg Gratings are created by modulating permanently the refractive index into the core of a standard optical fiber. This modulation is occurred using an intense ultraviolet (UV) source such as UV laser [16]. The amount of the periodic change at the refractive index depends on the intensity and duration of the controlled exposure to UV radiation as well as the photosensitivity of the fiber. The operating principle of FBGs is based on the measurement and the mathematical reconstruction of data derived from the propagation and reflection of light. Thus, it becomes possible to make an accurate characterization of the loading condition subjected to the material and consequently to the optical fiber.

More specifically, the fundamental purpose of a Bragg grating into the optical fiber's core is to reflect only the light signals at wavelengths which satisfy the Bragg condition or resonance condition of a grating. For a single mode and uniform FBG, the reflected light is centered on the Bragg wavelength λ_{B0} , which is directly related to the grating period Λ and the mean effective refractive index n_{eff} [17], through the Bragg condition $\lambda_{B0}=2n_{eff}\Lambda$. All the other light signals of a broadband light source, which are at wavelengths other than the Bragg wavelength, are not phase matched and for that reason are essentially transparent. The effective refractive index (n_{eff}) and the grating periodicity (Λ) are directly influenced by the strain and the ambient temperature. As a result, when uniform changes in strain and/or temperature occur, along the FBG, its spectral response exhibits a shift of the Bragg peak wavelength.

When the FBG sensor is embedded into a host material and assuming that the two lateral strains on the fiber ε_x , ε_y are related to the axial one ε_z by $\varepsilon_x = \varepsilon_y = -\nu_f \varepsilon_z$ (where ν_f is the Poisson's ratio of the fiber), the wavelength difference $\Delta\lambda_B$ obtained from the peak shift of the spectra, before and after loading, is given by the following equation:

$$\Delta\lambda_B/\lambda_{B0} = (1 - p_e) \varepsilon_{sol} + (1 - p_e) (\alpha_m - \alpha_f) \Delta T + (\alpha_f + \xi) \Delta T \quad (1)$$

In the previous equation λ_{B0} is the Bragg wavelength at a reference state, $\Delta\lambda_B = \lambda_B - \lambda_{B0}$ [12] is the difference in wavelength obtained from the peak shift of the spectra, before and after the loading, p_e is a grating gage factor which is measured experimentally [18] (where $p_e \approx 0.215$), α_f is the coefficient of thermal expansion of the fiber (where $\alpha_f \approx 8 \times 10^{-7} \text{ } ^\circ\text{C}^{-1}$ [19]), ξ is the thermo-optic coefficient of the fiber (where $\xi \approx 8.3 \times 10^{-6} \text{ } ^\circ\text{C}^{-1}$ [20]), ε_{sol} accounts for the solidification induced residual strains and $(\alpha_m - \alpha_f) \Delta T$ for the strains ε_T due to thermal expansion mismatch [21].

3 EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

The specimens investigated in the present work were manufactured on a Stratasys Dimension Elite FDM 3D printer. In addition, the materials used for the fabrication of the specimens were the commercial Acrylonitrile Butadiene Styrene (ABS) P430 as model material and the SR P400 as support material which is soluble. The built specimens had dimensions of 130 mm x 130 mm (width x length) as well as 13 layers of height (3.302 mm). These dimensions were chosen after a series of trial experiments, in order to assure good embedment of sensors within the samples of the subsequent experiments.

During the fabrication process, the ABS material is initially in a form of flexible filament, which is fed into a machine. The model material by the aid of a specific roller mechanism is extruded through a robotically controlled and heated deposition nozzle onto the building platform, after its melt. The liquefier temperature of the built material is approximately at 270°C and when the polymer filament is extruded from the heated nozzle, it cools and solidifies within a controlled envelope temperature environment, which is set to 70°C. Each specimen is manufactured by the subsequent deposition of layers, as the 3D printer's nozzle extrudes a thin layer of material onto the previously built model layer that has solidified. It is important to be mentioned that the layers of the ABS material start to be deposited onto the moving worktable, when the building procedure of the support layers is completed.

In the present work three different plate specimens were manufactured for the embedment of thermocouple sensors and the investigation of the in-situ temperature variations presented during the deposition of ABS material. Additionally to these experiments, three more plate samples were built, in order to incorporate FBG sensors within the structures and monitor in real-time the magnitude of the consolidation induced residual strains which are exhibited during specimens' fabrication process. Both the thermocouples as well as the FBG sensors were embedded within the middle plane of the plate structures. As mentioned earlier, the samples were consisted of 13 layers and for that reason, the incorporation of sensors were achieved after the completion of the 6th layer. The 7th layer is considered as the neutral axis of the laminate structures and as a result, symmetry is observed between the layers located above and below it. The processing parameters for all the types of specimens were kept the same. More specifically, the layer thickness of each specimen was 0.2540 mm and the raster orientation was set to $\pm 45^\circ$, representing the machine's default tool path orientation.

The sensors used to carry out these experiments were 0.25 mm K-type thermocouples and two different types of optical fibers. Short single mode optical sensors were used which were equipped with a Bragg grating of 1 mm in length and operating at a Bragg wavelength of 1550 nm, as well as FBG sensors with five multiplexed Bragg gratings and a grating length of 1 mm, each one operating at a different wavelength (1527 nm, 1540 nm, 1550 nm, 1560 nm and 1573 nm, respectively). Moreover, both types of FBG sensor had a core diameter of 0.125 mm and were coated with acrylate which had a thickness of 0.0625 mm. The spectrum measurements were taken using a Micron Optics sm125 optical sensing interrogator and the temperature data recordings were obtained and analyzed through a data acquisition instrument. The whole experimental setup that was used for each category of experiment (embedment of either FBG sensors or thermocouples) is shown in Fig. 1a-1b, respectively.

Figure 1: Experimental setup used for the recording of a) wavelength variations, b) temperature profiles.

In Fig. 2a-2b, the locations, in the middle plane, at which became the integration of thermocouples and FBG sensors are performed, respectively. In the first type of experiments conducted, the locations 1, 2 and 3 were selected for the embedment of thermocouples and single mode optical fibers, while in the second type of the plate specimens, the respective locations for the incorporation of sensors were the points 4, 5 and 6. Furthermore, in the last type of experiments performed, the measurements were obtained from the sensors which were embedded at the diagonal of the plates (+45°). The thermocouple sensors were located at the points 6, 2 and 7 whereas the five multiplexed Bragg gratings were positioned at the points 7, 8, 9, 10 and 11. As it is observed, the locations which were selected for the embedment of the sensors enable the real-time mapping of the developed residual strains and temperature profiles at a major part of the samples' plane and consequently of the overall structures. Placement of the thermocouples in the same layer and location with the optical fibers was considered important for the obtainment of accurate measurements and the proper evaluation of the experimental results.

Figure 2: The locations, in the middle plane, at which became the integration of a) thermocouples, b) fiber Bragg grating sensors.

The building process of the FDM plate specimens started with the deposition of a predefined number of support layers. When the last layer of the support material was completed, the layer by layer deposition of the model material (ABS) was enabled, until the structure reached the plane at which either the FBGs or the thermocouples would be integrated. At this point, the FDM 3D printer paused and the nozzle moved away from the specimen's surface, going back to its zero position. The printer's chamber opened and the sensors were placed on the surface of the last deposited layer. At the same moment, a reference Bragg wavelength (λ_{B0}) was obtained. Consequently the building process continued and the nozzle returned to the location where the layer deposition procedure had stopped, in order to deposit the rasters of the next layer. When the nozzle started to build the perimeter of the 7th layer, the continuous recording of measurements derived from either the optical fibers or the thermocouple sensors was initiated. The fabrication procedure continued until the whole plate sample was manufactured. At the end of the manufacturing process, the specimen remained onto the building platform and inside the printer's chamber for 20 hours, in order to cool down to ambient temperature gradually, and to avoid thermal shock of the final structure. It is important to be mentioned that for the embedment of the sensors at the correct location, some specific sets of "alignment holders" were designed and simultaneously built with the plate specimen. Furthermore, the thermocouples were securely fixed on the "alignment holders" with silicone and the FBG sensors with double-sided tape. Finally, in the case of the plate samples at which thermocouples were incorporated within the structures, the design and fabrication of specific slots was necessary to avoid the sensors' displacement from the nozzle, as the thickness of the thermocouples is relatively close to the layer thickness.

4 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The measurements obtained from the thermocouples as well as the FBG sensors contributed significantly in ensuring the validity of the followed experimental procedure and in the exportation of some very interesting in-situ results. In Fig. 3, the recorded temperature and wavelength variation as a function of specimen's build time are presented, respectively, for the locations 1, 2 and 3 at the structure's middle plane. The data for these locations were obtained in the first type of experiments which were conducted. As it is observed, both temperature and wavelength reach a peak value prior to a rapid decrease, as the nozzle departs from the region close to the sensor's sensing point. The building process until the completion of each layer has a duration of 500 sec. As a result, each of the three peaks presented to the values of each layer indicates the passage of the printer's nozzle exactly above the thermocouple or the optical fiber sensor. Moreover, the maximum values of temperature are recorded from the thermocouple at the location 1, while the minimum values are presented at the location 3 (Fig.3a). The same behavior is exhibited in the trend of the wavelength curves as a function of the plate's build time (Fig. 3b). Therefore, an important observation exported concerning these diagrams is that dependence between the wavelength and temperature values is present. In both charts a smooth declining pattern is seen at the recorded values of the sensors.

Figure 3: a) Temperature, b) wavelength variation as a function of build time for specimen with embedded sensors in location 1, 2 and 3.

In Fig. 4, the obtained temperature and wavelength changes are plotted as a function of the sample's build time for the locations 4, 5 and 6 which are quite close to the edges of the square plates. These locations were selected for the sensors' embedment at the second type of experiments which were conducted. It is noted that large fluctuations of the temperature profiles as well as the wavelength values are not observed after 1500 sec of the building time, exhibiting only a stable decrease.

Figure 4: a) Temperature, b) wavelength variation as a function of build time for specimen with embedded sensors in location 4, 5 and 6.

In the third category of specimens fabricated, the thermocouples and FBG sensors were incorporated at the plate's diagonal (+45°), in order to record in real-time the temperature and wavelength changes during the manufacturing procedure. The incorporation of thermocouples was achieved at points 7, 2 and 6, while the five multiplexed Bragg gratings were embedded in the locations 7, 8, 9, 10 and 11. In Fig. 5a, the presence of three temperature peak values which fully coincide at approximately 250 sec (7th layer), 1250 sec (9th layer), 2250 sec (11th layer) and 3250 sec (13th layer), respectively, arising from the +45° toolpath orientation of the nozzle which covers with one passage all the thermocouples. On the other hand, the -45° toolpath orientation of the nozzle results in the integration of each sensor at a different time. Therefore, during the fabrication process of the 8th, 10th and 12th layer, three asymptotically peaks at the temperature values are taking place. In Fig. 5b, the wavelength values, recorded in-situ by the multiplexed optical sensor, are plotted as a function of the build time. Each one of the plotted curves in the diagram represents the signal shifts obtained from the five Bragg gratings, separately, which were located at a different position. As it is observed, every 1000 sec a smooth change at the recorded wavelength values from all Bragg gratings is exhibited, prior to a rapid peak value. The smooth changes on the five curves are presented at the same time, while the peak wavelength values are shown in a different time period. This variation pattern of the curves is due to the 3D printer's default crisscross (±45°) raster orientation, resulting in either a simultaneous incorporation of the five Bragg gratings with the deposition of one raster or the embedment of one grating after the other. It must be noted that the Bragg grating located at the position 10, exhibits constant wavelength values after approximately 750 sec, because at that moment the signal was lost, not thus recording during subsequent measurements.

Figure 5: a) Temperature, b) wavelength variation as a function of build time for specimen with embedded sensors in location 7, 2 and 6.

Using Eq. (1) and solving for ϵ_{sol} , the magnitude of the solidification induced residual strains, at each Bragg grating location, can be calculated from the recorded peak wavelength values. It is noted that for the calculations, as reference Bragg wavelengths (λ_{B0}) are considered the values measured exactly before the deposition of the 7th layer. In Fig. 6, it is obvious that the magnitude of the developed strains during the fabrication process is significant reaching a mean value of 5500 and 6000 microstrains ($\mu\epsilon$), respectively. In Fig. 6a, the stable increasing pattern of the generated compressive strains is depended on the corresponding trend of the temperature and wavelength curves, which present a smooth reduction. In Fig. 6b, the fluctuations of the residual strains recorded in real-time arising from the corresponding variation pattern of the temperature and wavelength profiles, which are not stable at the first layers of the deposition procedure.

Figure 6: Variation of solidification induced residual strains as a function of layer number for specimen with embedded Bragg gratings in the locations a) 1, 2 and 3, b) 4, 5 and 6, respectively.

In Fig. 7, the generated residual strains reach a value of 5000 microstrains ($\mu\epsilon$), which is the same for almost all the gratings. The declination of the strain values calculated from the data derived by the Bragg grating located in the position 10, resulting from the failure of the grating during the building process. Examining Fig. 6-7, one can conclude that the solidification induced strains, measured at specific locations within the plate specimens, are generated when the very first layers are deposited while afterwards their magnitude does not change much with the subsequent deposition of layers.

Figure 7: Variation of solidification induced residual strains as a function of layer number for specimen with embedded Bragg gratings in the locations 7, 8, 9, 10 and 11.

5 CONCLUSIONS

In the present study, optical sensors were used for in-situ monitoring purposes in FDM built specimens. A series of plate samples were manufactured, in order to incorporate the fiber Bragg grating sensors in different locations within the middle plane of the structures. Temperature mapping of the fabricated specimens during the deposition process was also achieved. During the fabrication process the solidification induced residual strains were calculated from recorded FBG spectra, whereas the temperature variations were obtained from thermocouple sensors. The use of FBG sensors for real-time monitoring of the strain build up along with the structure's temperature history can greatly contribute to the collection of significant information concerning parameters mainly affecting the final mechanical properties of the fabricated element.

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